

A Study of Inclusivity in the Fashion and Textiles Industry

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Abstract:

Societal beauty ideals for women were always shaped by cultural, historical, and geographic factors that contributed to bias and discrimination. The fashion industry is witnessing a change, with inclusivity and diversity becoming the dominant trends, encompassing age, skin tone, ethnicity, sexual orientation, body size, etc. The fashion industry has recognized the importance of representing diverse voices and perspectives. This shift towards inclusivity and diversity is a positive development.

This study examines perceptions of inclusivity in the Indian textiles and fashion industries. A mixed-methods approach is used to study how these industries comprehend, embrace, and practice inclusivity.

The literature review explores size and gender inclusivity, body positivity, and the effects of social media on the fashion industry. It discusses how brands adopt inclusive approaches to marketing and the overall shopping experience. Luxury brands, once synonymous with exclusivity, align with the concept of inclusivity.

A survey of the Indian population indicated that respondents were knowledgeable about inclusivity in fashion, linking it to "Fashion for All." H&M and Zara were mentioned frequently when discussing inclusive brands in India. Respondents expressed willingness to support and potentially pay more for inclusive brands, although some expressed reservations about higher prices.

The fashion industry actively embraces diversity, challenges norms, and advocates inclusivity. Although progress has been made, significant gaps remain in creating authentic and inclusive fashion experiences to cater to diverse individuals. As the industry continues to evolve, embracing diversity, challenging conventions, and promoting inclusivity will continue to shape the future of fashion, making it a more accessible and empowering space.

Keywords: *Gender Inclusivity, Inclusivity, Indian Fashion Industry, Perceptions, Size Diversity.*

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1. Introduction

The perception of beauty has been transformed in the contemporary world, embracing a broader array of attributes. For centuries, societal beauty standards have propagated limited ideals, particularly for women. The quintessential attractive woman has been defined by a slender build, full bosom, narrow waist, curvy bottom, well-defined jawline, high cheekbones, full lips, rosy complexion, and long flowing hair. These standards have been shaped by cultural, historical, and geographical factors deeply rooted in biases and discriminatory attitudes. A slight deviation from these standards was considered exotic, whereas a substantial deviation resulted in individuals being deemed unattractive [1]. Consequently, these individuals were marginalized and excluded from mainstream narratives.

The fashion industry holds a prominent position in society, serving as a platform for self-expression, cultural representation, and identity formation. Fashion is inclusive and universally applicable, transcending the boundaries of age, gender, race, ethnicity, and body type. Fashion has become a global phenomenon, a language understood and spoken by many. The industry has witnessed substantial change, with diversity and inclusion emerging as dominant trends. Diversity in fashion entails promoting a diverse group of individuals who exhibit distinct

characteristics, such as age, skin color, race, orientation, and body type. People aspire to be heard, seen and represented [2].

Over the years, the fashion industry has significantly shaped societal norms and influenced individual perceptions. As fashion continues to evolve, there is a growing call for inclusivity, urging the industry to embrace diverse perspectives, challenge prevailing stereotypes, and celebrate individualities. Recently, inclusivity in fashion has garnered increasing attention, fostering a more equitable and representative industry that transcends traditional boundaries and norms.

Inclusion can be defined as ‘the act of including someone or something as part of a group, list, etc., or a person or thing that is included’ and as ‘the idea that everyone should be able to use the same facilities, participate in the same activities, and enjoy the same experiences, including people with a disability or other disadvantages’ [3].

The Oxford Language Dictionary defines inclusion as the practice or policy of providing equal access to opportunities and resources to people who might otherwise be excluded or marginalized, such as those with physical or mental disabilities or those belonging to other minority groups. From a historical perspective, access to clothing products has not belonged to every class for centuries [4].

1.1 Significance of the Study

This study investigates the extent of inclusivity within the Indian fashion industry, specifically its capacity to incorporate various body sizes and genders. India is renowned for its diversity, but there is a concern that its textiles and fashion sector may not fully represent or cater to this heterogeneity, potentially failing to meet contemporary consumers’ expectations of inclusivity.

This research endeavors to interpret how inclusivity is comprehended, embraced, and implemented in Indian fashion by analyzing the opinions and attitudes of individuals within this heterogeneous society. The findings of this study offer valuable insights to fashion industry stakeholders, thereby facilitating better alignment with evolving societal expectations for inclusive representation of diverse body sizes, genders, and beyond. Comprehending these perceptions and attitudes is crucial for the fashion industry to adapt and become more inclusive, aligning better with evolving consumer expectations.

1.2 Objectives

This study aims to fulfill the following objectives:

1. Evaluate the level of inclusivity in the textile and fashion sectors by reviewing the current literature.
2. Investigate the effects of social media on shaping perceptions of inclusivity through a review of existing literature.
3. Obtain opinions of the Indian populace concerning inclusivity within textiles and fashion spaces through an online survey.

1.3 Review of Literature

The fashion industry has always endorsed a particular standard of size, color, gender, and body shape that fashion publications and runways have widely promoted. However, not all consumers conform to these standards. Inclusivity aims to embrace and celebrate diversity in size, ethnicity, gender, and other characteristics by creating an environment where individuals of different backgrounds feel valued and welcomed [5].

Brands are now expected to cater to consumers of all body types by offering a range of sizes, from plus sizes (3XL and above) to smaller sizes (XS and below), and catering to various heights, from petite to tall. The demand for size inclusivity reflects collective consumer consciousness and changing attitudes [6].

Inclusivity extends beyond considering the body in clothing. Consumers have become accustomed to seeing various faces, skin colors, and styles on the runway and brands instead of having a uniform perception of beauty [4].

1.3.1 Body Positivity

The body positivity movement emerged as a social campaign to embrace all bodies, regardless of size, shape, skin tone, gender, and physical capabilities. The modeling agencies' constant demand for models to be "white, skinny, young, and female" was one of the first areas of fashion inclusivity to be publicly scrutinized. The body positivity movement has been hailed as "the biggest rebellion against the dearth of diversity and positive self-image in the fashion industry." The prevalence of eating disorders, diet, and the pursuit of perfection, which social media has aggravated, has been displaced by currents that encourage individuals to love and accept their bodies [4].

The body-positive movement has led to an increase in women's self-acceptance of their bodies, resulting in a rise in support for body-positive fashion brands [7].

1.3.2 Size Inclusivity: Plus Size

The fashion industry derives 15 percent of its revenue from the plus size. This market segment has evolved beyond dull colors and unflattering silhouettes to cater to the diverse needs of customers, maintaining its aesthetic identity across offerings of all sizes. Fit is as important as the availability of plus-size options. Moreover, Indian body types and sizing differ significantly from those in the US or UK, making it necessary for brands to invest in research to gather data to develop well-fitting garments for customers of all sizes [6].

Plus-sized customers often face insensitive treatment from the sales staff or feel judged by their size. Stores must prioritize sensitization and training of staff to ensure a positive shopping experience. Some customers prefer online shopping because of their convenience and ability to filter items according to size and fit [6].

1.3.3 Gender Inclusivity: Gender-Neutral Fashion

While it is common for women to wear men's clothing, men who wear women's attire receive less acceptance from society, suggesting the presence of underlying gender biases. Designers such as Rohit Bal and Arjun Saluja pioneered gender-fluid fashion in the early 2000s. Wendell Rodricks's gender-fluid collection at Lakmé Fashion Week 2007 disrupted gender norms, influencing designers to explore non-binary aesthetics. In the 2010s, celebrities and designers embraced and promoted gender-neutral fashion, culminating in Anjali Lama's historic walk as the first openly transgender model at Lakmé Fashion Week in 2017. In the 2020s, the fashion industry is endorsing unisex designs that prioritize comfort and self-expression, breaking the barriers of traditional gendered clothing [8]. The growing acceptance of unisex clothing signifies a shift towards openness and equality in society. Unisex fashion represents a step towards personal freedom and societal progress. There is an increasing demand for gender-neutral clothing in India, particularly in metropolitan areas, indicating a growing acceptance of gender diversity [9].

1.3.4 Role of Social Media in Promoting Inclusivity

Over the past decade, social media has emerged as an effective marketing tool that allows marketers to promote brand awareness among consumers. It is recognized as the most transparent, engaging, and interactive form of public relations [10]. Influencers and creators promote awareness and education, thus contributing to brand inclusivity [6]. An array of LGBT+ and plus-sized influencers strive to eradicate stigma and promote inclusivity by using social media to share educational messages [11].

Social media has changed fashion communication, giving visibility and a voice to communities that the fashion world has historically ignored [12]. The fashion sector employs social media platforms to study prevailing trends and predict consumer behavior. Social media have made the fashion industry more accessible to the public [10]. Consumers use social media platforms to showcase their support for those who feel excluded. Championing these changes on social media is essential to fostering a more inclusive and accepting society [11].

1.3.5 Steps Taken by Brands to be Inclusive

It is essential to incorporate inclusivity into a brand's marketing strategy. Featuring diverse individuals in promotional materials allows customers to envision themselves using a product or service. Collaborating with influencers and digital creators representing various sizes, genders, and body types is critical for brands that wish to engage with a diverse customer base. Modeling agencies must recruit models of diverse sizes, skin colors, and heights to ensure that no individual feels underrepresented, and mannequins should be produced in a range of sizes [6].

The luxury industry has attempted to include non-binary individuals in its marketing campaigns to challenge traditional norms. For example, Chanel launched a makeup line for men in Korea and recruited a transgender model to represent the brand. Recent developments in the beauty industry have led to a greater emphasis on diversity, with brands like Fenty and Dior offering over 40 different shades of foundation. Luxury brands adapt to clients from various social backgrounds by lowering the prices of certain items or by collaborating with bridge brands to make luxury products more accessible. Another strategy is establishing a "sister" brand, targeting a less affluent market. Such brands include Marc by Marc Jacobs, Must de Cartier, and See by Chloe. The United States is trending towards "affordable luxury brands," such as Michael Kors, Coach, and Kate Spade. This sector appeals to the younger generation, who can purchase "luxury" items at a significantly lower price [13].

Luxury is an integral aspect of the identities of brands such as Chanel and Dior; destroying it would equate to the end of their essence. These brands must democratize themselves intelligently and inclusively to maintain their positions in the market. They must balance inclusivity and exclusivity to maintain their unique identities [13].

Significant transformations have occurred in the fashion communication spaces. Editorial policies of conventional fashion publications show progress toward inclusivity by embracing the visual representation of previously excluded individuals in mainstream social narratives. Established and emerging photographers' works highlight imperfect faces, curved bodies, disabled physiques, and fluid identities. This shift in focus aims to broaden the perspective and overcome the limitations of the gaze by including those previously marginalized [14].

2. Materials and Methods

This study employs a mixed-methods approach to investigate perceptions of inclusivity in Indian fashion. To capture perceptions of inclusivity in fashion, a survey was administered to the general population through a Google Forms link. The survey used open-ended and close-ended questions to understand the nuances of individual perceptions. It consisted of demographic information to collect data on participants' age, gender, location, occupation, and socioeconomic background; a section on awareness and perception of inclusivity to evaluate participants' understanding of inclusivity in fashion and their familiarity with inclusive fashion brands; and a section on purchase intention and preferences to assess participants' willingness to purchase from inclusive fashion brands and their willingness to pay a premium price for inclusive brands.

2.1 Sample Size and Selection

Profile: Anyone over 18 years of age could participate in the survey.

Sample size: Three hundred questionnaires were sent, and 279 responses were received. The sample was selected using Convenience sampling.

3. Results

The fashion and textile industry has been criticized for promoting a narrow ideal of beauty that prioritizes specific physical attributes such as size, color, gender, and shape. There is a growing demand for inclusivity and diversity in fashion. The body positivity movement seeks to embrace individuals from all backgrounds and identities that challenge conventional beauty standards and promote acceptance and self-love for all bodies. Social media have played a significant role in this shift towards greater inclusivity and representation, as individuals and organizations have used these platforms to challenge stereotypes and share diverse perspectives. Brands have taken notice of this demand for inclusivity, offer more inclusive designs, and create a welcoming shopping experience for all customers. This shift is also reflected in the evolution of fashion magazines, which prioritize inclusive representation and authenticity, featuring a more comprehensive range of faces, bodies, abilities, and identities.

The literature review serves as a foundation for understanding the historical evolution of inclusivity within the fashion industry, its multifaceted dimensions, and its effects on individuals and societies. Drawing from this literature, the study focused on collecting primary data through a survey distributed among the adult population. The survey's primary objective was to investigate the perception and acceptance of the term "inclusivity" in the context of fashion among the Indian population.

The survey was administered to 300 individuals, and 279 participants provided their responses, yielding a response rate of 93 %. Of the participants, 73.1 percent were from Maharashtra, and 15.7 percent were from Delhi and the NCR. Of the respondents, 79.2 percent were female, 18.6 percent were male, and the remaining did not specify their gender. 44.8 percent of the participants fell within the age bracket of 35-44 years, 35.1 percent were in the 18-24 age group, and 14.3 percent were in the 25-34 age group. 26.1 percent of respondents reported a monthly family income of more than INR 500,000, 29.3 percent had an income between INR 100,000 and INR 250,000, and 31.1 percent had an income between INR 50,000 and INR 100,000. 42.2 percent of the participants held a Postgraduate degree, while 25.8 percent had a Bachelor's degree. Regarding occupation, 37.6 percent of respondents were employed, 40.1 percent were students, and 22.2 percent were entrepreneurs.

Participants were asked whether they identified with any of the "socially different" categories, such as being plus-sized, having dark skin, being transgender, being skinny, or having a disability, among others. The participants were allowed to select multiple options. A majority, 55.1 percent, chose the "none of the above" option, while others selected categories such as plus-sized, skinny, and dark-skinned. Regarding fashion, 36.5 percent of respondents

closely followed the latest trends, while 39 percent were somewhat aware of them. Only 20.7 percent were somewhat unaware, and only 3.8 percent were completely unaware of the latest fashion trends.

When asked about inclusivity in fashion, almost 62 percent of the respondents were familiar with the term, while 18.6 percent were not. The rest were unsure. When asked about what inclusivity in fashion means to them, varied responses summarized “Fashion for All” as the essence of inclusivity.

As shown in Figure 1, most respondents (65.9 percent) opined that an inclusive brand extended its reach to diverse sizes. Moreover, some contend that inclusivity encompasses catering to individuals from all socioeconomic backgrounds and those with disabilities. Additionally, inclusivity is linked to sustainability, encompassing a more comprehensive range of skin tones and cultural groups.

Figure 1: Which all statements according to you makes a fashion brand Inclusive? (Multiple options can be selected)

When asked if they were more likely to purchase from a brand that uses models similar in age, gender, and body shape to their own, 45.1 percent responded that it made no difference, while 37.7 percent said yes.

Regarding willingness to purchase genderless clothing, 55.1 percent responded with Yes, 17.2 percent with No, and 27.7 percent were unsure.

When asked about finding clothes that fit them in terms of size, color, budget, and help express their identity, a majority (36.5 percent) said they find such clothes sometimes, while 31.8 percent said they find them often. Around 19.6 percent always find the clothes that express their identity, while another 12.8 percent are rarely able to find such clothes, as seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: How often do you find clothes that fit you in terms of size, colour, budget and help express your identity?

As seen in Figure 3, when respondents were asked about inclusivity in the Indian Fashion Industry (brands), 37.7 percent indicated that certain brands are inclusive, 31.1 percent stated that only a few brands are inclusive and diverse, and 7.4 percent believed that the Indian fashion industry is not inclusive and diverse.

Figure 3: Is the Indian Fashion Industry (Brands) inclusive and diverse?

When asked about the brands they feel are inclusive, the respondents frequently mentioned H&M, Westside, Amydus, Zara, Marks & Spencer, TrueBrowns, Doodlage, Biba, AND, Global Desi, and House of Masaba.

Figures 4 and 5 show that 53.7 percent of respondents preferred Inclusive brands over other brands, while 39 percent would 'maybe' rate them higher. However, only 26.1 percent of respondents were willing to pay a premium price for an Inclusive brand, and 47.6 percent would 'maybe' pay a premium for an Inclusive brand.

Figure 4: Will you rate an Inclusive Fashion Brand higher than the one that is not?

Figure 5: Will you be willing to pay a premium for Inclusive fashion brands?

The study also reveals that individuals within the 18-24 age bracket exhibit a greater awareness of inclusivity. Approximately 80% of respondents from this group are familiar with the term, 57% rate inclusive brands higher than others, and 75% might be willing to pay a premium for such products. Additionally, this age group is the most inclined to purchase gender-neutral clothing.

In contrast, the 25-55 age group demonstrates lower levels of awareness, with only 49% of respondents familiar with the term inclusivity with respect to fashion. However, a higher percentage (50%) of this group rates inclusive brands favorably and may be willing to pay a premium. Approximately 42% of this age group expresses interest in purchasing gender-neutral clothing.

When examining gender differences, 62% of female and 45% of male respondents report being aware of inclusivity. Among these groups, 55% of females and 45% of males prefer to purchase brands that practice inclusivity, and 48% of females and 70% of males indicate they would be willing to pay a premium for such products. Furthermore, a similar proportion of male (50%) and female (50%) respondents express interest in buying gender-neutral clothing.

The survey indicated that Indian consumers prefer inclusive brands, highlighting the need for a varied size range, aesthetic accessibility, and diverse representation in marketing. To address this, brands should offer gender-neutral clothing, ensure accessibility to physical and online stores, conduct staff training for inclusive services, collaborate with diverse influencers, and research local sizing needs to better cater to the Indian market's unique requirements.

4. Conclusion

The study explores the concept of inclusivity in the textile and fashion industry, which seeks to challenge historical beauty standards and embrace diversity. The study employs a mixed-methods approach, utilizing a literature review and survey to understand perceptions of inclusivity in Indian fashion.

The literature review highlights the development within the fashion industry as it progresses from upholding rigid beauty standards to advocating for inclusivity and diversity. In the past, the industry favored the specific dimensions of size, color, gender, and shape. However, recent style trends indicate a shift towards accommodating a broad range of body types, ethnicities, and genders.

The body positivity movement has emerged to challenge these traditional norms, advocating for the acceptance of all body types, and resulting in increased support for brands that align with these values. Social media have played a crucial role in this transformation, promoting diverse representations and challenging stereotypes, thus shaping consumer expectations of inclusivity.

Gender inclusivity has also gained traction, with designers and brands introducing gender-neutral fashion, reflecting societal shifts towards non-binary and fluid gender identities. Luxury brands are adapting to these changes, balancing inclusivity with their exclusive image, and fashion communication is evolving to highlight their diverse and previously marginalized identities.

The survey targeted 300 individuals, yielding 279 responses, with a substantial portion originating from Maharashtra and exhibiting diverse demographics, including gender, age, and income. The majority of participants were educated and held various occupational positions. Regarding inclusivity in fashion, 62% were acquainted with the notion, primarily defining it as "Fashion for All," highlighting the importance of accessibility, diversity in sizing, and representation. Brands such as H&M, Zara, and others were acknowledged for their inclusive initiatives. Gen Z shows high awareness and preference for fashion inclusivity and gender-neutral clothing. Millennials and Gen X have lesser awareness but still support inclusive brands and show significant interest in gender-neutral options. Across genders, while females are generally more aware of inclusivity, males are more likely to pay a premium, with both genders equally interested in gender-neutral clothing. The survey disclosed the overall support for inclusivity and a nuanced perspective on its implementation and economic implications within the Indian fashion industry.

The fashion industry is increasingly recognizing the importance of inclusivity, which involves accommodating a diverse range of body sizes, shapes, and identities. Size inclusivity has become a significant aspect of the industry, with various sizes being offered to ensure that everyone feels represented and confident. Inclusivity in the fashion industry encompasses gender and cultural diversity. Social media has emerged as a critical platform for marginalized voices to influence and reshape fashion narratives, fostering global connections and community support. Inclusivity in fashion is becoming a core value rather than a trend, necessitating continuous evolution to meet consumer expectations and promote diversity. The industry's progress in embracing various identities and cultures signifies a move towards a more inclusive, representative, and empowering fashion future. This journey underscores the need to expand inclusivity, ensuring that fashion is a space where everyone feels seen, heard, and valued.

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